

E-COMMERCE: EVOLUTION, PRESENT STATUS AND FUTURE PROSPECTS**MISS SWETTA MOHANTY*****DR. BINITA NANDA****

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ABSTRACT

In the last two decades there has been a rise in the use of internet and mobile phones which has changed the way we communicate. By definition E- commerce can be defined as buying or selling of goods and services via internet. Given the impact of internet on all the aspects of life, e-commerce has augmented creating new source of opportunities for the business, industries, and an increase in employment opportunities. The emergence of E-commerce has led to providing number of opportunities to its users spread across enormous geographical areas. Studying e-commerce's evolution, its present status and analyzing its future prospective could prove beneficial as it will help us know its positive and negative aspects and would further help us to know the changes that are needed to be made for its smooth functioning. This paper aims towards studying the evolution of e-commerce, its present status and the future prospects associated with e-commerce.

KEY WORDS: Electronic commerce, e-commerce, Internet, Online, business

INTRODUCTION

E-commerce in simpler terms can be explained as the use of electronic communications and digital information technology for the purpose of business transactions to create, transform, and redefine relationship towards creating value among organization and individual. It can further be explained in simpler terms as is the expansion of traditional business operations into business operating in electronic space. It can be regarded as the most promising application of information technology as it has enabled the businesses to augment their internal efficiency and so far as to the expansion of their operations globally, and thus, surpassing geographical barriers.

E-commerce also can be referred as electronic commerce or internet commerce, refers to the buying and selling of products or services using the web, and therefore the transfer of cash and data to execute these transactions. E-commerce is usually used to the sale of tangible products online, but it also can be described as any kind of commercial transaction that's facilitated through the utilization of internet or using internet as a medium.

Most popularly, it's understood as the exchange of goods and services through an electronic medium. However, the utility of e-commerce is not limited to just sale and purchase of goods and services over computer networks, but, entails the entire online process of developing, marketing, selling, delivering, servicing and paying for products and services.

Types of E-commerce models based on the parties involved have been categorized into the following applications:

Business to Business (B2B)– It consists of all the electronic transactions between two h. Here a business sells goods and services to another business. Transactions between manufacturers and distributors, wholesalers and retailers, in other words all exchanges which involves businesses at both the ends

Business to Consumer (B2C) – When a business sells its goods and services to an individual customer.

Consumer to Consumer (C2C) –It involves all transactions of goods and services between consumers. For example: an online portal can be provided by a third party like ebay, which can be used by consumers to put second hand goods for auction or conduct other transactions.

Consumer to Business (C2B) – Here the consumers sells his own product or services to a business or organization.

REVIEW OF LITEERATURE

(Raghunath &Panga, 2013) concluded that initially, new internet users would be reluctant to conduct any kind of business online, citing security reasons as their main concern. In order to boost consumer adoption of e- services, the source of consumer confusion, apprehension and risk required

to be identified, understood and elevated. E-Commerce provides tremendous opportunities in several areas but it requires careful application for consumer protection issues

(Dasgupta&Sengupta, 2002) in their paper examined the future and prospects of e-commerce in Indian Insurance Industry

Nisha Chanana and Sangeeta Goele (2012) the article entitled “Future of E-commerce in India”.In this article an attempt has been made to focus on the overview of the future of E-commerce in India and discuss the long term growth of segments of E-commerce in India. The findings of the study were the various factors that were essential for future growth of Indian E-commerce. The study also found that, the overall E-commerce will increase exponentially in coming years in the potential market of India.

(MadhukarSarode, 2015) in his paper concluded that E-commerce is future of shopping and gap has been reduced between manufacturer and consumer due to e-commerce. There is vast scope for e-commerce in India but due to weak cyber law, people are facing challenges in India

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY:

1. To study the evolution of e-commerce
2. To analyze the present status and future prospective of e-commerce in India

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research methodology involves specific techniques that are adopted in research process to collect assemble and evaluate data. It defines those tools that are used to gather relevant information in a specific research study.

This paper is a conceptual paper based on descriptive analysis using various secondary data and includes different literature reviews, published sources of data collected from various research papers and data from various website.

The Evolution of E-Commerce:

Instant access is one among the foremost fascinating features of the web. The introduction of World Wide Web has led to explosion of e-Commerce, which has successively changed the way we work, socialize, and also has brought a drastic change in shopping experience for consumers. Over the past few decades, the internet has grown into the required medium for marketing, advertising, and buying of products, goods, and services; e-Commerce has grown rival to traditional shopping in some ways.

History of evolution of e-commerce

1960 – 1990

- Electronic Data Interchange (EDI) was invented that helped to share invoices and receipts.
- Trading data format (ANSI ASC X12) was set as the standard form for sharing document in North America.
- The VAN (Value-Added Network) was called as the standard for shopping order examination.
- Michael Aldrich, an English entrepreneur, is taken into account as the pioneer for inventing teleshopping.
- France launched Minitel, an online free service for telephone subscribers.

1990 – 1994

- Hypertext project
- World Wide Web

1995 – 2000

- Amazon as the first online bookstore was founded by Jeff Bezos
- Another success of E-commerce story is an online auction site, **eBay**.
- The **first catalog-based store** for e-commerce market was launched by Miva.
- **Worldwide products** distribution started over the Internet.
- **Dell** was ranked as the mega online distributor for achieving one-day online sales of \$1 million.
- **PayPal** started its services as the first global E-commerce company

ANALYSIS OF PRESENT STATUS AND FUTURE PROSPECTIVE OF E-COMMERCE:

E-commerce is currently making tremendous changes which in turn transformed the traditional way of shopping beyond expectations. From being a buzz word then into now becoming the order for the day e-commerce have changed a lot with the passage of some years. People seemed to be literally shopping anywhere and everywhere – for e.g. at their workplaces, lunch hours, during the rush hours, for their leisure when there is nothing else to do.

E-commerce have gained so much of fame because of its core i.e. technologies that are budding and blooming out. So why step out somewhere, when all you have to do, is place an order, choose the shipping method, put up your feet and wait till the order, is delivered right at your doorstep.

Online shopping at its early stage was a simple yet complicated medium for doing purchases with a fewer choices available. The users then found it to be a little difficult to use. But in the last few years there has been renovation done in this field to a great extend and hence this fascinated many customers. Today, shopping using internet has become a trend in India and therefore the reason behind the adoption of this system lies within the attractive online websites, user friendly interface, variety of online stores with new fashion, easy methods of payment (i.e. secure pay online via gateways like paypal or cash-on-delivery), no bound on quantity & quality, one can choose the items based on size, color, price, preferences etc.

There has been a praiseworthy increase in the industry of E-commerce, despite of India being a developing country and thereby hitting the market with a boom. The Indian online market is at its growing stage.

Further, the add-on of discounts coupons, offers vouchers, referral code systems, 30days guaranteed return policy, fastest delivery time, etc. to the online shopping and the E-Market have added new flavors to the E-commerce industry.

- The Key drivers of in Indian E-commerce have been:
- Increasing use of Internet and 3G penetration.
- Growth in the Living standards
- Availability wide range of products
- Busy lifestyles
- Increasing evolution in the online market place with websites like amazon, Flipkart, Snapdeal, etc.

PRESENT STATUS OF E-COMMERCE,

Social Media as a Lead Generation tool

Social media has now become the hub for the merchants which enable them to research the customer choice supported their purchase activities. Social network like LinkedIn, Twitter, Google+, Facebook et al. became a medium for straightforward log-in and buy. Moreover, the clients can stay updated via the posts published on this media. Further, the advertising & promotions on these social sites has increased the probabilities of success of generating transactions to several folds.

Mobile Commerce:

The latest trend in e-commerce is mobile based shopping. Snapdeal is now getting half its traffic from mobile, up from 5% around a year back and flipkart gets 40% traffic from mobile up from 15%. As price of smart phone reduce, these figures will only increase. For this reason, the larger E-commerce firm has started that specialize in mobile commerce. It's speculated that subsequent wave of digital commerce consumer will come through the mobile.

Price comparison engine:

In the race to accumulate customer, e-commerce sites offer deep discount and these discount vary from site to site depending upon its capacity to barter with the supplier. To urge the simplest discounts, buyer got to search a plethora of web sites. Here, Price comparison sites are available like mysmartprice.com, Pricedekho.com, and Junglee, etc. The web sites compare prices over the whole web and supply users with the simplest available price. E-Commerce sale through these website are increasing and can further increase as consumers get more and more discount savvy.

Online Grocery Store:

Online grocery stores are gaining popularity in India due to the absolute convenience, simple shopping and a fast-growing market. Punexpress.com, Milestore.com, Atadaal.com, Amazon pantry have already entered the market and are gaining popularity. They supply discounted product and free home delivery. All of those stores are targeting the Indian housewives, who are yet to get into e-commerce way of shopping.

Advancement in logistics:

The addition of the new concept within the E-commerce industry had been recently observed when Amazon patented its new delivery model called the Prime Air which is predicted to be launched within the upcoming years. This model will use the highly technically embedded drones or helicopters for the moment delivery of the things. These are going to be programmed in such a way that employing a GPS system they're going to identify the precise address for delivery and drop the item right ahead of the doors of the purchasers. These aerial vehicles will prioritize the general public safety and are designed as per the commercial aviation standards.

Latest E-commerce Trends in India

The digital world is in a state of constant flux, and here, trends emerge every day. Online marketing is not just limited to advertisements but has developed its roots in several sectors like social media, experiential marketing and much more. Latest trends which are aiding the e-commerce sector's growth are:-

1. Niche Based Product Placement Advertising

E-commerce has started advertising with differing types of videos which appeals to the proper customer niche at the proper time. Brands have started approaching people through movies or vines which individuals wish to watch, and influencers became important during this respect. Tiktok and YouTube became the most important approachable video platforms for product placement advertisements

2. Marketing Automation

E-commerce companies have started contextually connect with users supported their behaviors. Marketing automation is enabling these companies to remain connected with users once they are close to make a sale.

3. Customized Messages

Customization is getting more important than generic messages. People pay more attention to personalized messages and wish to answer them.

4. Mobile-Friendly or Responsive Websites

E-commerce sites are getting more mobile-friendly as people spend tons of your time on their mobiles. E-commerce has gone mobiles through apps and straightforward loading websites which make buying consumers easier and keep them connected with their favorite brands.

5. Augmented Reality

Augmented reality product pictures also are a crucial trend for sellers in e-commerce because it provides an interactive experience to customers with product. They experience products features closely and obtain more deeply engaged with the products than a traditional picture.

6. Snap to buy

E-commerce has given a feature of clicking your favorite product's picture and buying it or visiting the merchandise page. People can now snap pictures of things they like and may get the merchandise on websites.

Scope of E-Commerce in India is driven by Young Generation

According to the UN report India is considered as the youth capital of the world. Hence it can be considered as the focus demographic for e-commerce operators anywhere in the world. So in a country like India where the use of internet is growing in cycle with the aspiring youth of the nation, foresees enormous amount of opportunities for the e-commerce to flourish.

FUTURE PROSPECTIVE OF E-COMMERCE:

It is a fact that E-commerce in India is not possible without access to the internet. According to a 2018 study published by Pew Research Centre, only 25% of the Indian adult population uses the web regularly. Again, the use of internet is restricted to urban and semi-urban areas. Lack of proper infrastructure plays a huge role in restricting the access to the internet for our citizens. Moreover, in remote areas, owning a cell phone with internet access is still a dream for the poor people.

However, the situation is changing, and fast. India is a highly competitive market for the telecom service operators- this has led to intense price wars, which have progressed to cheap internet usage rates among service providers, much of benefit to the customers.

E-commerce Buyers in India

India has one of the fastest growth rates of digital explosion in the world. India's internet penetration took a massive leap of 24.23% in between 2007 to 2017 according to a study by the Aranca.

In 2007, the penetration rate was just 4%. As of Dec 2018 it had reached at 42%. It implies that approximately 566 millions of Indians have internet access. Out of which 493 million (or 87% population) are active internet users.

From the projections above it is implied that the number of internet users in India is more as compared to several other countries combined. There exists huge potentiality which is to be unlocked in the electronic commerce sector.

The growth of E-commerce in India with the Rise of Digital Payments

The growth of E-commerce in India is led by and co-existed with- the increase in digital payment methods and platforms. Online payment has turned out to be boon for busy customers, who often do not seek out time to go to a bank. What was once restricted to only net banking for paying utility bills and services, has today transformed into a huge sector. Today, we can pay our utility and even consumer bills from our cell phone.

There are several apps and digital payment platforms that are available. Since most people now are cautious of carrying large amounts of cash, digital payment has become their most preferred way. Sensing the preference of the consumers, more and more companies are now enabling digital payments- and as a result, snagging the digitally savvy customers.

This has also turned out to be a blessing to small businesses and startups. Enabling digital payments helps them in catching the attraction of more number of customers. This is the reason behind many companies encouraging digital payment via their own developed apps or other preferred partner's platforms while offering attractive discounts, offers to the legit customers.

The Government of India has been actively pushing up for the large-scale adoption of digital payment method- which is a hassle-free, convenient, fast, and eco-friendly. This has been crucial to the "Make in India" movement by the govt. of India which aims at fostering indigenous entrepreneurs. With digital payments becoming more popular, it has now turned out to be possible for them to conduct transactions with clients, customers and suppliers from all over the world.

With the launch of UPI and Bhim, more people are now paying online- a development that is already showing a significant increase in sales for online retailers.

The scope of E-commerce in India

According to a study by PwC and Nasscom, it can be estimated that the Indian E-commerce market may grow more than fourfold to \$150 billion by 2022, fuelled by rising incomes and a pitch in internet users. The Indian middle-class population is also growing, which implies a rise in the

number of aspiring consumers. Companies will do well by reaching out to them- because there is a massive market potential which is waiting to be unlocked.

The study projected that the amount of internet users is predicted to just about double to 850 million in five years. Among them, 150 million users are expected to carry out digital transactions and they will mainly be based in tier-2 and 3 cities. These customers can take advantage of diverse language choices available for surfing the internet, payment modes and products.

It can be assumed that growth in the E-commerce sector will involve the growth of all significant sectors- e-travel and e-ticketing, e-tail, financial services such as e-wallets and insurance, consumer services (classifieds and e-services) and digital content segments.

Challenges in E-commerce in India

While E-commerce is booming in India, it is also not without its pitfalls. Here are some challenges that the sector is facing in India:

- 1. Internet is Still a Dream for Some-** There are still some places where people don't have access to the web.
- 2. Lack of Clear Cyber Laws-** India lacks in proper cyber laws, and people are still afraid of getting duped online by fraudsters. On the opposite hand, lack of clarity in regulation and loose property laws also leave an enormous window for fraudsters to duplicate or pirate products.
- 3. Lack of Quality Control-** E-commerce is successful in providing products door to door but unfortunately, in most cases, there's no check on the standard. People often find yourself getting totally various things, or what they get is remarkably different in quality than what they see on websites.
- 4. Online Transaction Security-** People are still not confident with online payments as they need fear of getting their account details leaked.
- 5. Delivery Delays-** Delivery dates goes on extending which is a major challenge for the E-commerce users

Conclusion

E-commerce industry is one of the largest growing industries at present. The sales of e-commerce industry is expected to grow by almost 4 times by 2023. It goes without saying that there is a massive market for E-commerce in India, and it is expected to grow even more. This is due to increase use of internet, smart phone users, availability of 3G/4G services at cheaper cost, government initiatives towards digitalization, online shopping and E-commerce are also expected to grow proportionately. The E-commerce sector is not only expanding and growing but also dynamic in nature which makes constant changes in terms of consumer needs and preferences, advancement in technology and various offerings of product. Small businesses, retailers should get themselves prepared for the future digitally. As more number of customers go online and seek out for various product and services, anyone who doesn't keep themselves updated will be left behind

However, there are some drawbacks in e-commerce such as delivery issues, security issues, consumer's trust, international legislation such as custom, and product description defeats. There are hopes of overcoming these drawbacks with the arrival of far better technology within the near future. All aspects of businesses has its strengths and weaknesses and it all depends on personal preferences on how one could oversee the drawbacks and reap in the benefits of this technology to form the simplest use of the great technological advantages.

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